

Some Trivalent Lanthanide Complexes of 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin^ψ

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The lanthanides have long been known as blood anticoagulant¹. They have been used as biological probes². The rare earth complexes of plumbagin (2-methyljuglone) have been reported along with their antimicrobial activity³. Coumarins have been found to exhibit physiological activity. Since 8-acetyl-4-methylumbelliferone exhibits anticoagulant and plant-growth regulant properties, it was considered of interest to study the rare earth complexes of the biological active ligand. The present communication describes the synthesis of the complexes of 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (AHMC) with trivalent La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy.

Results and Discussion

The complexes (Table 1) have high melting points and are soluble in methanol, ethanol, dimethylsulphoxide and dimethylformamide. The molar conductance values of the complexes at 10⁻³ M dilution in methanol are in the range 4–13 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹, suggesting their non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic moments of all the complexes observed at room temperature (292 K) indicate that all except La are paramagnetic. The observed magnetic moments of all the complexes agree closely with Van Vleck values⁴.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES *

Compd.**/ (Colour, Decomp. Temp. °C)	Analysis % : Found/ (Calcd.) Metal	μ _{eff} B.M.	Mol. cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
[La(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (White, 380)	10.37 (10.46)	Diam.	6.0
[Pr(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (Red, 290)	10.64 (10.79)	3.44	13.0
[Nd(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (Red, 245)	10.82 (10.95)	3.53	12.8
[Sm(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (Brown, 365)	11.09 (11.28)	1.64	4.7
[Gd(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (Red, 385)	11.54 (11.60)	7.70	5.6
[Dy(L) ₂ H ₂ O Cl] (Red, 195)	11.81 (11.92)	10.55	7.6

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl analyses.

**L = C₁₂H₁₀O₄

A broad band is observed at 3 300–3 000 cm⁻¹ (OH coordinated water) in the ir spectra of all the complexes⁴. The presence of coordinated water is further confirmed by the appearance of a non-ligand band at 840–850 cm⁻¹ assignable⁵ to rocking modes of water. The absence of ν_{OH} (phenolic) band (occurring at 3 500 cm⁻¹ in the ligand) in the spectra of all the complexes suggests the cleavage of intramolecularly hydrogen-bonded⁶ OH and subsequent deprotonation of the phenolic group and coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal ion. The ν_{C=O} ligand band (1 700 cm⁻¹) position is lowered in the complexes, showing thereby coordination through ketonic group which is confirmed by pmr (CH₃-C=O) δ shift in the complexes (which is at δ 2.9 in ligand). The metal-chlorine band is present at 335–365 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. New bands observed at 600–450 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{M-O} modes.

The characteristic bands observed in the electronic spectra of the Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes have been attributed to the transitions from ground levels ³H₄, ⁴I_{9/2} and ⁶H_{5/2} respectively, to the excited J levels of 4fⁿ configuration, indicating O_h geometry for the complexes. The electronic spectra of the complexes indicate shift in frequencies on complexation towards wavenumber relative to aquo ions⁷, indicating that 4f orbitals do not participate much in bonding. The nephelauxetic ratio β (= ν_{complex}/ν_{aquo}), covalency factor b^{1/2} and Shihua metal-ligand percentage covalency parameter⁸ have been calculated. The values of β being less than 1 (0.955–0.992), show the covalent nature of bonding between the lanthanide ions and ligand. The greater the values of covalency factor, b^{1/2} and δ are, the greater is the degree of covalency. The separation of the bands in AHMC and aquo complexes of the order of ~500 cm⁻¹ shows that these complexes are distorted octahedral. The thermal behaviour of the complexes is almost identical, hence only that of [Pr(C₁₂H₁₀O₄)₂.H₂O.Cl] is being discussed. The DTG curve indicates the decomposition in two steps at 110–148 and 195–385°. The loss of water molecule occurred at 146° with a mass-loss of about 2.7% (theoretical 2.85%). The organic moiety starts decomposing after 380°. The formation of Pr-oxide and CO₂ is indicated at 407° with mass-loss of 72.40% (theoretical 73.84%). Pr-oxide is the end-product.

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Experimental

The lanthanide(III) chlorides were obtained from Rare-Earth Products (India). The ligand was prepared by the reported method⁹.

The metal complexes were prepared by mixing a solution of the ligand in nitromethane with lanthanide chlorides (M : L ratio 1 : 2). On heating and vigorous stirring, the whole mixture turned red (except for La complex). The resulting solid was isolated by centrifugation, washed several times with the chloroform and dissolved in methanol. The solution was then concentrated and the complex reprecipitated by adding chloroform. The product so obtained was dried by keeping it for several days *in vacuo* over phosphorus pentoxide.

The analysis and physical measurements were performed as reported earlier¹⁰.

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